

Social Structure and Cultural Change in Humanities: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Social Structure in sociology is the distinctive, stable arrangement of institutions that enable humans to interact and live together. Culture is an indispensable component of social life. This article contains a systematic literature review. In addition, books and scholarly articles from EBSCO, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect were selected for the literature and data. The studies were published in English and peer-reviewed were sampled. Three reviewers assessed the search results, extracted data, and evaluated the quality of the studies to summarise and report the findings. It revealed that social structure is discussed alongside the concept of social change, which examines the forces that alter society's social structure and organisation. Social structure is how to recur patterns in social life. Social change and cultural change refer to alterations in an individual's personality. However, one change is associated with social actions and the other with the cultural environment. Fundamentally, social change entails adopting societal changes rooted in feminism or women's empowerment. The change that occurs within the confines of society. On the other hand, cultural change is in the form of change associated with particular social groups. Cultural change demonstrates its direct effects on social transformation. This is a review article; the recommendation is to contribute quantitative and qualitative research in further study for insights, results and explanations in behavioural analytics adopting psychological theories.

Keywords: Social structure, Cultural changes, Humanities, Psychology, Behaviour

INTRODUCTION

Recent works in literary and cultural studies, sociology, political science, anthropology, history, and art history have become more spatially oriented. They assert, from various vantage points, that space is a social construction relevant to the comprehension of the diverse narratives of human subjects and the production of cultural phenomena. In some ways, this transformation is expressed in simple semantic terms, i.e., the literal and metaphorical use and assumptions of "space," "place," and "mapping" to denote a geographic dimension as an essential aspect of cultural production (Warf & Arias, 2008). A genuinely integrative trend must recognise the 'autonomous ontological status' of ideation with human agency and social structures to include the ideational aspects of social realities as the third dimension in its agenda. Nonetheless, due to current global changes and the emergence of new modes of consciousness, it is necessary to reformulate our notions of knowledge and cognition under a new concept (Hosseini, 2012). The goal of the development of humanities education in the information society is to implement an

interdisciplinary approach, i.e., to ensure the effectiveness of the development and application of humanities knowledge and to foster cultural self-determination (Kravtsov et al., 2020). Social structure is essential in encompasses groups, institutions, laws, population characteristics, and sets of social relations that form the organisation's environment. The social network comprises all variables that are stable, extra-organizational characteristics of the society (Stinchcombe, 2000). Better techniques and more data have made it possible in recent years to identify systematic differences in people's preferences and beliefs and to relate them to various measures of cultural legacy. These advancements suggest a testable strategy for incorporating culturally based explanations into economics, which may significantly enhance our understanding of economic phenomena (Guiso et al., 2006). Thus, social structure and cultural changes are crucial in humanities.

LITERATURE REVIEW Social Structure

The structure was defined in terms of behaviour: In actuality, the structure is thought of as a form of stable or repeated behaviour. It is relatively simple to construct the macro level from the micro level, given that structure is behavioural. The microstructure consists of a small number of individuals repeating their behaviour, while the macrostructure consists of many individuals repeating their behaviour. In social explanation, the explanatory dynamic must be at the micro level. Social structure cannot be a significant independent variable because abstractions lack causal forces. Macro social structure is predominantly epiphenomenal. Similarly, the microstructure is epiphenomenal for the same reason. Given that it is merely an abstraction with no independent effects, it is unclear whether the structure is a beneficial concept from this perspective (Porpora, 2013). There are three primary reasons why social structure influences economic outcomes, particularly in the form of social networks. Social structures affect both the quantity and quality of information. Since much information is subtle, nuanced, and difficult to verify, actors rely on private sources rather than impersonal ones. Second, social networks are an essential source of rewards and punishments, as these are frequently amplified when emanating from personally known individuals. Third, trust emerges, if it does, in the context of a social network. By this, I mean the confidence that others will do the "right" thing despite a clear imbalance of incentives to the contrary (Granovetter, 2018). Individual differences in positive psychological functioning and a multidimensional formulation of psychological well-being are essential. Sociodemographic variation (such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status) is exciting. Community and national sample data will illustrate how broad life course and social structure influence shape well-being (Black, 2014). Moreover, conceptualising gender as a structure places gender on the same level of social significance as the economy and the government. While intersectionality must remain of utmost importance, different structures of inequality have other constructions and possibly different influential causal mechanisms at any given historical time (Risman, 2018). Therefore, the structure is a form of consistent or recurring behaviour. Since the social structure is behavioural, constructing the macro and micro levels is relatively straightforward.

Language as Social Action for Social Structure

Using lexical strategies rather than inflectional morphology to encode evidentiality, negation, aspect, and possession is significantly more prevalent in languages spoken by large populations. Language structures appear to adapt to the environment (niche) in which they are learned and utilised. As adults acquire a language, it becomes less likely that difficult-to-learn characteristics will be transmitted to future learners. The languages used for communication in

large groups, including adult learners, appear to have been subjected to this selection. In contrast, the morphological complexity typical of small-group languages increases redundancy, which may facilitate language acquisition in infants (Lupyan & Dale, 2010). In bilingual conversation, the conversational structure relates to the social structure to the extent that language itself is a social structure, i.e., to the time that language structures society. In turn, this is merely a matter of taking seriously the frequently invoked concept of linguistic identity. Concerning the issue of the interaction between language alternation and non-linguistic social structures, a significantly broader theory of interpretive processes in conversation is required (Gafaranga, 2005). Because different languages provide different terms, cultural perceptions may vary. Similarly, basic attributive techniques may be constrained by the language of the perceiver. A language that provides an abundance of dispositional terms may increase the likelihood that these terms will be used, thereby increasing the likelihood that internal rather than external attributions for behaviour will be made. Implicit causality is the most apparent attributional effect of language; the verbs used to describe actions can convey information about the presumed causes of those actions. Although this may not reflect linguistic determinism strictly, there is an asymmetry in the causal locus of many verbs, which may bias people's attributions (Holtgraves, 2013). Recently, economists have begun to view linguistic structures as important determinants of economic phenomena. There are intricate relationships between language, culture, thought, and behaviour. The relationship between linguistic structures and economic and social outcomes is supported by empirical evidence (Mavisakalyan & Weber, 2018). Thus, language is the social action for social structure.

Social Structure and Economic Outcomes

How social relations influence behaviour and institutions is one of the fundamental questions of social theory. In contemporary industrial society, economic activity is embedded in social relations structures. Even though conventional neoclassical accounts offer an "under socialised" or atomized-actor explanation for such behaviour. Under- and over-socialised accounts are paradoxically similar in their disregard for ongoing structures of social relations. A sophisticated understanding of economic action must account for its embedding within social structures (Granovetter, 2018). Sometimes structure refers to structured wholes, and sometimes it refers to the connections or relationships that structure in entirety. Consideration is given to the social structure as structure-as-whole and structure-as-relationships. At times, the social structure relates to structure-as-empirical-regularity, whereas at other times, it refers to structure-as-properties. Additionally, structure-as-properties can refer to the properties of a social whole or the properties of human individuals, and social structure is embodied in the habitus (ELDER-VASS, 2007).

Creating Changes in the Humanities

The term "humanities" encompasses, but is not limited to, the study of language, both modern and classical; linguistics; literature; history; jurisprudence; philosophy; archaeology; comparative religion; ethics; the history, criticism and theory of the arts; those aspects of the social sciences that have humanistic content and employ humanistic methods; and the study and application of the humanities to the human environment with a focus on reflection (Unsworth, 2006). All society disciplines are currently being profoundly influenced and even transformed by the opportunities afforded by digital devices; as a result, the behaviour of scholars has undergone a revolution. This revolution is more profound than in the natural sciences, which were equipped to handle numerical and highly formalised data from their modern inception (Collins et al., 2015). According to computerised societies (remember, this

was 1979; the web did not exist, and the first desktop computers had just been introduced), a global monopoly of information maintained and protected by private companies or nations is a dystopian possibility. Google was founded roughly twenty years later with a somewhat different mission: to make the world's information universally accessible and helpful (Presner, 2010). While most mobile money transfers were gifts, there were also instances of borrowing and lending between family and friends, all of which occurred within relationships of trust, obligation, and need (ibid). In such circumstances, financial groups and mobile money transfers operate within egalitarian social relations, in contrast to the hierarchical and unequal power relations of conventional banks (ibid). Without access to borrowing, savings in financial institutions are primarily one-way transactions that do not reflect the nature of friendship and mutually supportive relationships, which are facilitated by reciprocal digital transfers (Haider, 2018). Thus, behavioural changes are related to social sciences and humanities.

Social Structure and Cultural Changes

Culture consists of explicit, implicit, and patterns for behaviour acquired and transmitted by symbols, constituting the distinctive achievements of human groups. The essential core of culture consists of traditional (i.e., historically derived and selected) ideas and especially their attached values; culture systems are the result of the action; however, culture systems may also be viewed as a system of ideas and values (Spencer-Oatey & Franklin, 2012). Several changes have been documented in cultural products, practices, and values because cultures are not static. The theories and insights from cultural evolution and social ecology are juxtaposed. Evolutionary approaches facilitate an understanding of the how of cultural change by proposing transmission mechanisms through which the contents of culture may alter. Ecological approaches shed light on the reasons for cultural change (Varnum & Grossmann, 2017). The required transformation in healthcare and medicine structure has not kept pace with the rapid development of the medical technology industry, despite the rising cost of treating chronic conditions and impending doctor shortages around the globe. This transition is slowed by strict regulations, the unwillingness of healthcare stakeholders to change, and the disregard for cultural shifts and the human element in an increasingly technological world. As the access to and adoption of technology increases, the likelihood that patients will rely primarily on an accessible but unregulated technological solution for their health problems will rise (Meskó et al., 2017). The limited creative reuse of data depends not only on the limitations of existing technologies but also on several social and cultural practices whose repercussions must be thoroughly addressed and investigated. If the full potential of linked data is realised, there must be a profound cultural shift in the production, management, and dissemination of data (Barbera, 2013). Students enrolled in pedagogical degree programmes have grown up with technology and are classified as millennials; therefore, it is necessary to describe certain aspects of their digital culture to better orient their initial teacher training and future professional performance, when all teachers will be digital natives. Some aspects of the current cultural paradigm with students pursuing a degree in pedagogical humanities inquired about the students' general characteristics, cyberculture, level of software usage, technological device usage, and digital skills (Ayala-Perez & Joo-Nagata, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Purposive sampling is when researchers utilise their knowledge to select the most beneficial sample. This method is commonly employed in qualitative research. The objective is to acquire extensive knowledge (Sitthipon et al., 2022; Limna et al., 2022). Texts are typically the starting point for qualitative content analysis. The goal is to condense a substantial amount of text into a

highly organised and concise summary of key findings (Jaipong et al., 2022). The researchers conducted a comprehensive review of the relevant literature and analysed the data using content analysis. In addition, English-language, peer-reviewed articles from ScienceDirect, PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science were included for data collection and analysis. Five independent reviewers examined search results, extracted data, and assessed study quality to summarise and report the findings. The collection and analysis of data took place between July 15 and August 20, 2022. The selected 26 articles out of 357,000 from 2000 to 2022 were included in this study and analysed by adopting content analysis.

RESULTS

The foundation of the beliefs shapes people's lifestyles, creates religions, and even sparks community conflicts. Thus, culture denotes a patterned way of living and thinking or the collective programming that distinguishes members of a given social group from those of other groups and is transmitted from generation to generation. Culture changes over time because each generation imparts distinctive characteristics to future generations. The objective of the development of humanities education in the information society is to implement an interdisciplinary approach, i.e., to ensure the efficacy of the development and application of humanities knowledge to the social structure concerning cultural changes. Social structure is essential because it comprises the groups, institutions, laws, population characteristics, and social relations that make up an organisation's surroundings. The social network includes all stable, non-organizational characteristics of society. In recent years, improved methods and increased data have made it possible to identify systematic differences in people's preferences and beliefs and relate them to various measures of cultural legacy. These developments suggest a testable strategy for incorporating culturally based explanations into economics, which could significantly improve our comprehension of economic phenomena. Sometimes social structure refers to structure-as-empirical-regularity and other times to structure-as-properties. In addition, structure-as-properties can refer to the properties of a social whole or the properties of human individuals, and the habitus embodies social structure. Culture consists of explicit, implicit, and behaviour patterns acquired and transmitted through symbols, constituting the unique accomplishments of human groups. The essential core of culture consists of traditional (i.e., historically derived and selected) ideas and their associated values; culture systems are the result; however, culture systems can also be viewed as a system of ideas and values.

CONCLUSIONS

The cultural change and social structure appear to have affected the languages used for communication in large groups, including adult language learners. In contrast, the morphological complexity typical of small-group languages increases redundancy, which may aid infants' language development. In bilingual conversation, the conversational structure is related to the social structure to the degree that language is a social structure, i.e., to the degree that language structures society. Consequently, this is simply a matter of taking the frequently invoked notion of linguistic identity seriously. Concerning the interaction between language alternation and non-linguistic social structures, a significantly broader theory of interpretive processes in conversation is necessary. Because cultures are not static, numerous changes in cultural practices and values have been documented. Cultural evolution and social ecology

theories and insights are juxtaposed. Evolutionary approaches facilitate an understanding of the how of cultural change by proposing transmission mechanisms through which the cultural content may change. Ecological approaches illuminate the causes of cultural transformation. Technological adoption is a prime example of cultural changes related to social structure. As the access to and adoption of technology increases, the probability that everyone will primarily rely on an accessible but unregulated technological solution for their health problems will increase. The limited creative reuse of data is contingent not only on technological limitations but also on social structure and cultural shifts. Students enrolled in pedagogical degree programmes have grown up with technology and are classified as millennials; thus, it is necessary to describe certain aspects of their digital culture to better direct their initial teacher training and future professional performance when all teachers will be digital natives. Some aspects of the current cultural paradigm with pedagogical humanities students inquired about the students' general characteristics, cyberculture, level of software usage, technological device usage, and digital skills.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is a review article and may not cover respondents' perceptions, which is the limitation. The recommendation is to consider empirical research, such as quantitative and qualitative studies. Additionally, it is suggested to consider a quantitative study, such as online surveys. A qualitative approach, including interviews and focus groups, may also provide a clear view of the results of an investigation.

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